

SynthRSF: a Novel Photorealistic Synthetic Dataset for Adverse Weather Condition Denoising

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Abstract: This paper presents the SynthRSF dataset for training and evaluating single-image rain, snow and haze denoising algorithms, as well as evaluating object detection, semantic segmentation, and depth estimation performance in noisy or denoised images. Our dataset features 26,893 noisy images, accompanied by the associated ground truth images. It further includes 13,800 noisy images accompanied by ground truth, 16-bit depth maps and pixel-accurate annotations for various object instances in each frame. The utility of SynthRSF is evaluated by training unified models for rain, snow and haze removal and receiving good objective metrics as well as excellent subjective results in comparison with previously published adverse weather condition datasets. Furthermore, we demonstrate its use as a benchmark for the performance of an object detection algorithm in weather-degraded image datasets.

1 INTRODUCTION

Designing and applying scene understanding models has become a central goal in both computer vision research and associated industrial applications. Such tasks can involve object detection, segmentation, depth estimation, as well as more complex procedures. However, in outdoor cases, adverse conditions such as rain, snow and haze, as well as variable lighting conditions, can impact the performance of such algorithms by causing degradation in the visual data. Computer vision degradation can be an important consideration in a range of applications, such as autonomous driving, surveillance, robotics, computer-assisted search-and-rescue, and more.

Image denoising or enhancement algorithms can attempt to mitigate this effect by applying a preprocessing step, restoring input images to a clearer state

before a computer vision algorithm is applied to them. Naturally, the quality and performance of such denoising algorithms directly impact subsequent vision tasks.

Rain, snow and haze are probably the most common weather conditions that are important for image restoration. In the deep learning era, a large count of research works on computer vision problems related to these subjects have been published. Due to the practical constraints of collecting rain, snow and haze-specific data with an associated ground truth at real-world sites, as well as the difficulty of defining the ground truth scene at a later time, when lighting and other variables have changed, significant research effort has been devoted to generating synthetic datasets for these weather conditions. Only recently, a novel technique was published (Ba et al., 2022) for generating ground truth for rainy images. However, similar approaches for other important weather conditions are still missing in the scientific literature.

In addition, existing adverse condition synthetic datasets are markedly dissimilar to real footage. Although some use real images as background and layer synthetic noise on top, the result appears flat and unconvincing to a human observer. Furthermore, by

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simply layering the weather noise on top of an image, one does not account for the effect of the weather phenomenon on the landscape nor the effect of existing lighting conditions on the appearance of the weather phenomenon itself. For these reasons, deep learning models trained on such datasets often perform poorly in real-world conditions, as the domain gap between the training set and the actual input during an application is significant.

A solution to the above would be a photorealistic synthetic dataset which included adverse weather effects not as a layer over a background image but as fully integrated 3D effects that are part of a scene. In recent years, modern game engines have drastically increased the quality of their graphics and are now capable of producing highly realistic scenes, incorporating not only objects, weather effects and lighting, but also the interactions between them. Exports from such scenes can comprise multiple versions of the same view, including ones with adverse weather conditions of various types and intensities, as well as clear ground-truth images.

This paper presents SynthRSF (Synthetic with Rain, Snow and Fog), a novel, photorealistic, synthetic dataset focused on incorporating adverse weather conditions, created using the Unreal 5.2 game engine. Although the dataset is fully synthetic, its use of 3D scenes, 3D weather conditions, and 3D lighting produces more realistic results than the 2-dimensional overlay approach used in existing datasets.

SynthRSF is based on 14 3D scenes, of various sizes (from indoor rooms to entire cities) set in various environments (urban day, urban night, interior, nature), within which the camera moves on a virtual rig, rendering images containing various types of noise: snow, rain, uniform and non-uniform fog. Each noisy frame is accompanied by the corresponding ground truth image, for training denoising models.

To showcase SynthRSF’s added value in visual computing research, a series of experiments has been conducted, using it to train the state-of-the-art *TransWeather* (Valanarasu et al., 2022) adverse weather noise removal model. As a training dataset, SynthRSF exhibits promising performance compared to existing adverse weather datasets, and beyond state-of-the-art performance when used in combination with some existing datasets.

In addition, a human subjective evaluation survey is performed, using real-world images taken in adverse weather conditions. Results provide compelling evidence that when training models with photorealistic data, denoising results are consistently deemed preferable by human observers.

Furthermore, SynthRSF comes with an additional

multi-modal expansion dataset, named SynthRSF-MM. The multi-modal dataset contains 14 scenes, with pixel-level annotations for 5 object instances per scene, and 39 object classes that are included in total. With its additional modalities, it can be used as a train and/or test dataset in a wider range of computer vision tasks, such as object detection, image segmentation, depth estimation, and scene understanding, with possible applications in autonomous driving, robotics, search-and-rescue, and more.

Hence, the main contributions of this paper can be summarised as follows:

- the **SynthRSF dataset**, a synthetic photorealistic dataset incorporating 3D weather effects and lighting, comprising 26,893 pairs of images (degraded with adverse weather and ground truth). The dataset, along with its expansion (see next bullet) is available on Git.¹
- the **SynthRSF-MM expansion**, an additional 13,800 pairs with ground truth on additional modalities: depth map, semantic segmentation, and bounding box pixel coordinates for 39 classes.
- a novel **Dataset creation methodology** based on the Unreal 5.2 game engine, leveraging 3D models and effects and predefined virtual camera paths, used to create SynthRSF and SynthRSF-MM.
- a set of **Experiments** comparing SynthRSF to previously published adverse weather datasets in training image restoration models.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses related work: existing weather-condition datasets, adverse weather modeling, synthetic dataset generation. Section 3 describes the design, generation, and content of the proposed SynthRSF dataset. Section 4 presents quantitative and qualitative experiments showcasing the added value of SynthRSF for image denoising and object detection benchmarking in adverse weather conditions. Finally, Section 5 provides a conclusion of the paper’s achievements and outlines future work.

2 RELATED WORK

This chapter explores the relevant literature on multiple domains that need to come together to provide a better understanding of the motivation behind, as well as the implementation of, the dataset. In order to create this dataset, the authors explore the modelling of

¹SynthRSF dataset repository

the visual occlusions of rain, snow and fog on an image. Then, the literature on unified denoising methods is reviewed, as well as the datasets that have been used so far. Finally, a short review is made on the novel category of fully synthetic game engine datasets.

2.1 Unified weather denoising models

When working with denoising methods, it is important to note the shift that has transformed the field, from earlier optimization-based techniques to deep-learning approaches, especially around 2017 and onwards (Yang et al., 2019). Optimization-based methods often require priors that are tailored to specific types of weather conditions, while deep-learning techniques are more likely to be used to model multiple phenomena. The advent of CNNs and GANs (Ren et al., 2020) has set the stage for much higher denoising performance.

So far, the fraction of works that perform unified deraining, desnowing and dehazing is still significantly smaller than the research work that targets rain, snow or haze in isolation. However, in the last few years only, multiple methods have emerged that follow a unified approach (Li et al., 2020), (Valanarasu et al., 2022), (Özdenizci and Legenstein, 2022), (Wang et al., 2023), (Chen et al., 2022), (Karavarsamis et al., 2022a). The authors of (Li et al., 2020) are one of the first that attempt to handle multiple weather degradations using a single network. The model architecture is based on CNNs and consists of multiple weather-specific encoders and a single common decoder. Furthermore, the performance of the network is enhanced using neural architecture search techniques. (Valanarasu et al., 2022) proposes a single encoder-decoder architecture based on transformers and uses weather queries to handle multiple adverse weather conditions. A novel transformer-based block is also proposed improving the networks' performance. (Wang et al., 2023) is another work based on transformers. To improve the learning capabilities and efficiency of the model, transformers-based blocks are used in a grid structure. The approach proposed by (Özdenizci and Legenstein, 2022) is based on denoising diffusion-based methods. Particularly it introduces a patch based diffusive restoration architecture enabling arbitrary sized image processing.

2.2 Datasets based on real images with synthetic weather effects

There is extensive past literature on rain-specific, snow-specific and haze-specific methods. The proposed dataset is suitable for training and evaluating

unified algorithms. The literature dedicated to such unified models is rather short. On the contrary, there is a vast literature dedicated to the single-image deraining, desnowing, and the single-image dehazing problem. For each of these problems alone, there exists very extensive prior literature on task-specific datasets.

For each single phenomenon denoising task, most methods use one or more of the following datasets, which have been documented in (Yang et al., 2020) and (Karavarsamis et al., 2022b).

Table 1: Datasets for Single Image Deraining, Desnowing, and Dehazing

Rain	
Dataset	Citation
Rain12600	(Fu et al., 2017)
Rain12000	(Zhang and Patel, 2018)
Rain1400	(Fu et al., 2017)
Rain800	(Zhang et al., 2019)
Test100	(Zhang et al., 2019)
Test1200	(Li et al., 2016)
RainTrainH	(Zhang and Patel, 2018)
RainTrainL	(Zhang and Patel, 2018)
Rain200H	(Yang et al., 2017)
Snow	
Dataset	Citation
Snow-100K	(Liu et al., 2018)
CSD	(Chen et al., 2021)
SRRS	(Chen et al., 2020)
SITD	(Li et al., 2019a)
Haze	
Dataset	Citation
I-HAZE	(Ancuti et al., 2018a)
O-HAZE	(Ancuti et al., 2018b)
D-HAZY	(Ancuti et al., 2016)
NH-HAZE	(Ancuti et al., 2020)
RESIDE	(Li et al., 2018)
FRIDA	(Tarel et al., 2010)
FRIDA2	(Tarel et al., 2012)
HazeRD	(Zhang et al., 2017)
BeDDE	(Zhao et al., 2020)
4KID	(Zheng et al., 2021)
REVIDE	(Zhang et al., 2021)

2.3 Fully synthetic game engine datasets

There is a significant contribution in the object detection literature, of fully synthetic datasets generated in game engines such as Blender and Unity 3D. Important milestones include SceneNet (Handa et al., 2016) containing annotated 3D scenes that can generate unlimited ground truth training data, (Richter

et al., 2016) who use games and their interaction with graphics hardware to generate labeled data and (Mayer et al., 2016) who provide a stereo video dataset to estimate disparity and scene flow. It is worth mentioning the paper on Sintel (Butler et al., 2012) which creates a new optical flow dataset derived from a 3D animated short film. To the best of our knowledge, weather noise has not yet been implemented in any fully synthetic game engine datasets.

It should be noted, as with any form of synthetic data, that there may be a domain gap that needs to be adapted to. Domain adaptation for synthetic datasets in deweathering involves aligning the representations learned by the model in the source (synthetic) domain with those of the target domain. This can be approached by either understanding the shifts in the data distribution (Albanis et al., 2021) or in deep-learning approaches such as (Ganin and Lempitsky, 2014) who achieved remarkable results using a large amount of synthetic data and limited real-world data.

3 The SynthRSF Dataset

3.1 Design

The design goal of SynthRSF is to create a collection of photorealistic image pairs in different types of environments, of weather-degraded images and their corresponding clear ground-truth image.

This is approached by adapting high quality realistic 3D Scenes, by adding 3D weather effects simulating rain, snow and fog. This way, included weather noise can be parameterized, in order to create numerous parameter combinations resulting in a wide range of visibility conditions.

The incorporation of three-dimensional weather effects, as well as their interaction with scene lighting has the potential of producing images that are much more realistic than the layered approach that has been used in many previously published datasets.

A particularly unique case is the modeling of fog. Real-life fog has two properties: it is both a cause of occlusion (it obscures what is behind it) and simultaneously it interacts with existing light sources, increasing the illumination of parts of the scene, whether in front or behind it. This type of simulation,^{2 3} has now been made possible with state-of-the-art game engines.

²Lumen Global Illumination

³Volumetric Fog

Table 2: Image contents per scene of SynthRSF. Unreal Documentation. Fog (U) and Fog (NU) stand for uniform and non-uniform fog respectively.

No	Description	Snow	Rain	Fog (U)	Fog (NU)
1	CitySample day	3862	10758	522	430
2	CitySample night	2695	2744	-	-
3	Hillside Sample	485	412	254	308
4	AngryMesh W1	279	287	180	211
5	AngryMesh W2	400	377	171	170
6	ICVFXProdTest	-	-	8	14
7	Realistic Rend.	-	-	75	75
8	Archviz Interior	-	-	-	30
9	Factory	-	-	13	16
10	Office Vol. 1	-	-	45	38
11	Bedroom Vol. 1	-	-	246	203
12	Kitchenette	-	-	3	15
13	Megascans A. A.	-	-	19	42
14	MeerkatDemo	250	250	51	55
	Total	7971	14828	1487	1607

3.2 Environment

The content environment of SynthRSF is based on 14 3D scenes designed in the Unreal 5.2 game engine⁴

Scenes are sourced from the Unreal Engine’s documentation, including Unreal’s City Sample Project and Hillside Project, which contribute most of the images of the dataset, due to the quality and variety of the 3D assets contained. Other scenes include the ICVFX production demo, Realistic Rendering demo, Archviz Interior and additional scenes obtained from the Unreal Marketplace. Unreal Marketplace links for each 3D Scene asset are included in the dataset folder.

These scenes have been selected in order to simulate a variety of environment and lighting characteristics: urban/rural, day/night, indoor/outdoor, wet/snowy. Within each scene, a virtual camera moves along predefined paths, capturing thousands of unique views. In keeping with the goal of achieving a high level of visual realism, interior environment scenes do not come with snow or rain noise. However, we do include interior scenes with uniform or non-uniform fog, as it has similar characteristics to light smoke and can be useful in applications related to emergency response.

Scenes 1-5 can be divided between the training and test sets without risking data leakage, as the camera does not revisit the same locations in its path. Specifically, the training set includes 67% of the images from scenes 1-5, along with all images from scenes 6-14. The test set comprises the remaining

⁴<http://www.unrealengine.com/>

33% of the images from scenes 1-5.

SynthRSF provides 26,893 weather images of rain, snow, uniform fog and non-uniform fog as analysed and summed in Table 3. This novel addition of non-uniform fog to a dataset of this kind is the reason behind SynthRSF’s name including “fog” rather than “haze”. All images are accompanied by their ground-truth pairs.

The full contents of the SynthRSF dataset are available for review in the dataset’s Git repository.¹

3.3 Weather effect implementation

Weather drops or flakes are simulated using a sprite material that is mounted on a particle from Unreal’s Niagara System. Speed and density ranges have been adjusted based on the desired visual outcome to resemble common existing web images.

3D weather effect generation is a major departure from the commonly used method of overlaying rain and snow masks on pre-existing images, since in real-life images, the concentration of raindrops and snowflakes in the visual field is proportional to the depth distance from the camera and their apparent size is inversely proportional to their distance from the camera.

Snow and rain are simulated in a virtual scene by combining elements: Particles (sprites) that represent close to medium-distance occlusion and a fog component that simulates light diffusion that is caused by snow and rain in larger distances. Particle dimensions, particle velocity and angle, particle population as well as fog effect density are variables that are being assigned sinusoidal functions with a different period per variable. This way, as these variables follow their sinusoidal function in a longer time, all their possible combinations are represented in SynthRSF.

Two types of fog are implemented in SynthRSF’s scenes: Uniform fog and non-uniform fog. Uniform fog is created by Unreal Engine’s ExponentialHeightFog module, while non-uniform fog was generated using the Unreal’s Legacy particle system.

Blueprint functions for the snow and rain effects are included in the dataset repository so they can be modified and reused by the community.⁰

An equivalent focal length of 18mm equivalent was used. Images were rendered through Unreal Engine’s movie render queue, with a custom rendering preset that is also provided in the dataset folder⁰.

3.4 The SynthRSF-MM (Multi-Modal) set

3.4.1 Motivation and functionality

Scenes constructed in 3D game engines inherently include the knowledge of the camera position, assets’ positions relative to the camera, as well as the shape and nature of each asset. Hence, additional ground-truth modalities can be included in each sample, including depth, segmentation, and object bounding boxes.

SynthRSF-MM, is an expansion to SynthRSF, containing fewer samples but including additional ground-truth modalities. It features 13,800 noisy images generated from 14 Unreal-Engine-sourced scenes. SynthRSF-MM’s scenes have been manually populated with 39 classes of 3D objects, including persons, vehicles, animals, etc. Subsequently, 3D weather effects simulating rain, snow and fog are added to the scene, similar to the SynthRSF main dataset. Each image is accompanied by a 16-bit depth map, pixel-accurate segmentation per object instance and YOLO-compatible bounding box .json files.

With its additional ground truth metadata, SynthRSF-MM can be used in additional tasks besides image restoration, such as monocular estimation, semantic segmentation, and object detection, both in clear and degraded conditions.

Because of the amount of manual labour involved in setting up objects for detection, this was unfeasible to do in the main SynthRSF dataset, where the goal was producing a large number of images with the maximum diversity of landscapes and noise to aid in training denoising models. For SynthRSF-MM, 825 unique static camera views were set up, and 8 noisy images per phenomenon (rain, snow, fog), per view, were generated. Indoor scenes feature fog noise only.

3.4.2 SynthRSF-MM Content

Depth maps Depth maps are available for each frame, enabling general-purpose tasks that reuse these depth maps. For instance, the information in depth maps can be used in conjunction with object detection to model the distance of objects relative to the camera. Figure 1 (a) and (b) show an example of a depth map and its ground truth image from SynthRSF-MM.

Object pixel-level annotations Object or semantic segmentation is an important task for domains such as autonomous driving, where bad weather noise can degrade the quality of images and impede segmentation algorithms in correctly extracting the boundaries

Figure 1: A sample scene from SynthRSF-MM, showing the ground truth (clear) scene, depth map, semantic segmentation stencil mask, and three noisy variants with different weather conditions. For each Ground truth image, there is one depth map, five pixel-level annotations and 8 noisy images per phenomenon.

Table 3: SynthRSF-MM contents

No	Description	Ground Truth	Depth	Snow	Rain	Fog (NU)
1	CitySample day	226	226	1808	1808	1808
2	CitySample night	158	158	1264	1264	1264
3	Archviz Interior	32	32	-	-	256
4	Factory	32	32	-	-	256
5	OfficeVol1	102	102	-	-	816
6	Bedroom Vol 1	22	22	-	-	176
7	Kitchenette	22	22	-	-	176
8	MegascansAA	20	20	-	-	160
9	MegascansSnow	20	20	160	160	160
10	Desert	17	17	136	136	136
11	MeerkatDemo	21	21	168	168	168
12	ICVFXProdTest	21	21	168	168	168
13	AngryMesh W1	21	21	168	168	168
14	AngryMesh W2	21	21	168	168	168
	Total	825	825	4040	4040	5720

of objects. SynthRSF-MM provides semantic segmentation ground-truth masks, similar to the SYNTHIA dataset (Ros et al., 2016), which can be used to either train or assess the accuracy of segmentation algorithms. Figure 1 (c) shows an example stencil mask and its paired fully synthetic color image from SynthRSF.

Object bounding boxes Object detection bounding boxes are available for calculating the accuracy of an object detection task. SynthRSF-MM provides a total of 39 classes out of the 80 target classes of the YOLOv8⁵ object detector. The 39 remaining target

classes were omitted because they were contextually irrelevant to the existing scenes. Objects which are either completely occluded or partially occluded with fewer than 100 pixels appearing on the camera visual field are not being allotted a bounding box.

4 Experiments

A set of experiments were conducted to evaluate SynthRSF and test its added value in computer vision research. The objective is to demonstrate that the use of SynthRSF in the training of weather-denoising deep learning models, either exclusively or alongside previously published datasets, can improve performance in real or realistic conditions.

In testing SynthRSF and comparing it to previous datasets, *TransWeather*, a widely used state-of-the-art deep learning model for restoring images degraded by adverse weather is employed. Experiments compare the results of *TransWeather* when trained by its default training dataset (*AllWeather*), SynthRSF, or a combination of both.

Three different experiments were conducted:

1. Objective comparison using PSNR and SSIM metrics, tested on various subsets of *AllWeather* and SynthRSF.
2. Subjective comparison on real adverse weather images. Application on real images is of course the ultimate goal of adverse weather denoising,

⁵<https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>

and can have different results compared to synthetic images due to the domain gap. As there is no ground truth available for real images, a subjective assessment experiment was employed.

3. Object detection comparison. A primary goal of image restoration is the subsequent improved performance of other computer vision tasks, such as object detection. This experiment compares the efficiency of YoloV8 on images restored by *TransWeather*, when trained on different datasets.

The following subsections provide details and results on these experiments.

4.1 Training an image restoration network for adverse weather conditions

4.1.1 Architecture selection

As SynthRSF is a dataset consisting of clean and noisy image pairs for three bad weather degradation types, specifically snow, rain, and fog, it is suitable for unified bad weather removal architectures (i.e. “all-in-one” models that can remove multiple weather conditions) (Valanarasu et al., 2022), (Özdenizci and Legenstein, 2022), (Li et al., 2020). The presence of such architectures is rather limited in scientific literature, especially if one considers their public availability.

Three such publicly available models were identified and tested: *TransWeather* (Valanarasu et al., 2022), *WeatherDiffusion* (Özdenizci and Legenstein, 2022), and *AirNet* (Li et al., 2022). Out of these, *TransWeather* features good robustness combined with a relatively fast training process; *WeatherDiffusion*, although superior in quality, is extremely slow both in training and inference, as also stated in the publication itself; and *AirNet* proved to be unstable at times due its contrastive learning approach.

Hence, the decision was made to employ *TransWeather* alone to conduct our experiments, allowing multiple training iterations and testing on tens of thousands of samples.

4.1.2 Training and testing datasets

In the original publication, *TransWeather* is trained on the AllWeather dataset. AllWeather is a combination of images drawn from three different datasets: Snow100K (Liu et al., 2018), Outdoor-Rain (Li et al., 2019b) and RainDrop (Qian et al., 2018) which contain images with snow, fog/rain and raindrop degradations respectively. In recent years AllWeather has become the go-to dataset for unified models. As such,

it was chosen as the dataset with which to compare the performance of SynthRSF. For the evaluation process three instances of *TransWeather* are utilised on distinct datasets: (a) the original AllWeather dataset; (b) the proposed SynthRSF dataset; and, (c) the combination of both datasets by using all images as input. Combining datasets as done in (c) often produces highly desirable results, as the literature (Liu et al., 2019; Yao et al., 2023) suggests. In the evaluation of these model instances, following the existing literature, the combination of Snow-100KL (snow) and test1 (rain, fog), which are the corresponding test sets for Snow100K and Outdoor-Rain is utilized, as well as the test set of SynthRSF (snow, rain, fog). Images with raindrop noise (drops of rain on glass) were not used either for training or testing. In the training process, the high-resolution image pairs of SynthRSF were downscaled from 1920x1080 to 720x405 pixels.

4.1.3 Training parameters

While training, *TransWeather* the default settings mentioned in the paper (Valanarasu et al., 2022) are used without alteration to any of the hyperparameters. To be precise, an Adam optimizer is used with an initial learning rate of 0.0002, which is annealed by a factor of 2 after 100 and 150 epochs. The network is trained for a total of 200 epochs and a batch size of 32. All models are trained on a single NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU using the PyTorch framework (Paszke et al., 2019).

4.1.4 Quantitative results

To evaluate the performance of the models we use the PSNR and SSIM metrics. The results for Snow-100KL, test1 and SynthRSF test set are summarized in Table 4. A few conclusions can be drawn from the results. As expected, the model instance trained on the combination of the datasets demonstrates the best overall performance. Furthermore, using SynthRSF in combination with AllWeather improves the performance of *TransWeather* for Snow100KL while not hurting the performance for test1. On the contrary, when testing SynthRSF test set, AllWeather does not seem to improve but rather diminishes the performance of the model when used in combination with SynthRSF. This showcases the effectiveness of SynthRSF when used in combination with existing datasets and highlights the complete nature and efficiency of our proposed dataset when used on its own. However, it is worth mentioning, concerning both datasets, that an instance trained on data resembling the testing data is expected to perform better.

Table 4: Quantitative results based on PSNR and SSIM for *TransWeather* trained on AllWeather, SynthRSF, their combination and tested on Snow100K-L, test1 and SynthRSF test sets.

Train \ Test	Snow100K-L (AllWeather snow)		test1 (AllWeather rain and fog)		SynthRSF Snow		SynthRSF Rain		SynthRSF Fog		Average	
	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM
AllWeather	28.08	0.86	27.17	0.87	24.83	0.79	24.33	0.73	20.07	0.73	24.90	0.80
SynthRSF	19.85	0.69	15.33	0.60	27.68	0.85	27.89	0.83	25.17	0.82	23.18	0.76
AllWeather + SynthRSF	28.39	0.87	27.16	0.87	27.48	0.85	27.82	0.83	24.66	0.82	27.10	0.85

4.1.5 Qualitative results

Synthetic datasets: The predictions of the three model instances for images of the three test sets are illustrated in the Figures 2, 3 and 4. Similarly to quantitative results, the usage of SynthRSF appears to improve model performance, especially for the case of fog removal.

Real world images: Even though the metrics for the test sets can be insightful, the performance of the model instances when using real world bad weather images could be considered of greater value. In Figure 5 the results for real world data are depicted. In this case, the effectiveness of SynthRSF is more apparent. All model instances showcase good denoising results, but the instances that used SynthRSF either by itself or in combination with AllWeather outperform the one that uses AllWeather only. Especially for the case of fog removal, the instance trained using only SynthRSF gives excellent results that appear to be better even than the one that uses the combination of the two datasets. The instance trained solely on SynthRSF effectively removes even the farther and denser fog element, while on the contrary the instance trained solely using AllWeather struggles to remove fog particles even at close distances. The good results on real-world data serve to prove this work’s initial hypothesis, that even though SynthRSF is synthetic, its incorporation of 3D weather effects and lighting produces realistic results that lessen the domain gap with real images.

4.2 Subjective assessment experiment

In order to evaluate training by SynthRSF in comparison with previous datasets, tests are performed on 75 real-world images collected from the Internet. Although a ground truth clear image for such cannot exist, and hence numerical results are not applicable, qualitative comparison can be performed on a subjective level.

Those images were fed to the three previously

trained *TransWeather* models, and the results were shown, in random order for each original image, to 70 survey participants.

Table 5: Subjective assessment experiment - Summary of data from 70 survey participants for the total votes per model, and the number of times each model was chosen as the preferred option across 75 noisy images.

Training set	All- Weather	Synth-RSF	Both
Rain			
Total votes	149/1167	610/1167	408/1167
Top voted image	1/21	12/21	8/21
Snow			
Total votes	381/1773	795/1773	597/1773
Top voted image	3/30	15/30	12/30
Fog			
Total votes	149/1567	911/1567	507/1567
Top voted image	1/24	18/24	5/24

The results of the survey are summarized in the table 5. The instance trained with SynthRSF, AllWeather and their combination are respectively preferred in the case of 45, 5 and 25 out of 75 images. A number of observations can be made on these results. Firstly, the participants show a clear preference for images restored using the instance trained on SynthRSF. This holds true for all cases of bad weather, but the preference in the case of “foggy” and “rainy” images is much stronger towards SynthRSF than in the “snowy” images, in which the total votes are more evenly distributed.

Despite the model trained on AllWeather often performing better in removing individual snowflakes or rain streaks, the model trained on SynthRSF, because of its fog data, tends to shift images towards higher contrast and to clean up the distant parts of the image that are obscured by the fog-induced light scattering. As fog is often, implicitly, a part of rain and snow scenes, as these phenomena tend to merge into

Figure 2: Qualitative results of denoised images from AllWeather test1 (rain and fog) dataset.

Figure 3: Qualitative results of denoised images from AllWeather Snow100K-L (snow) dataset.

Figure 4: Qualitative results of denoised images from SynthRSF dataset.

a fog-like blur in medium and long distances, this behaviour results in more distinct details, clearer to a human observer.

Similar indications of strong fog removal performance for SynthRSF were observed in quantitative and qualitative results discussed earlier, further cementing the survey findings.

4.3 Benchmarking an object detector on denoised images

4.3.1 Benchmarking YoloV8 on Synthetic noisy images

As a test case for SynthRSF-MM, it is used to benchmark the performance of YOLOv8 on images containing adverse weather noise as well as their denoised counterparts. As testing data, the COCO validation dataset is used, with overlaid snow masks from CSD (Chen et al., 2021) and SRRS (Chen et al., 2020) datasets, as well as rain masks from RainTrainL (Zhang and Patel, 2018) dataset.

For fog the COCO dataset does not provide depth maps thus making the creating of “foggy” effect on the images challenging. Instead we opt to use the RTTS dataset (Li et al., 2018) which simultaneously

Table 6: YOLOV8 results on COCO validation test degraded by CSD/SRRS snow masks

	map50	map50-95
noisy	0.623	0.466
AllWeather	0.629	0.468
SynthRSF	0.605	0.447
AllWeather+SynthRSF	0.632	0.471

Table 7: YOLOV8 results on degraded with rain coco validation set

	map50	map50-95
noisy	0.626	0.466
AllWeather	0.615	0.455
SynthRSF	0.616	0.457
AllWeather+SynthRSF	0.628	0.466

provides noisy images and bounding box annotations.

Results were favourable across the board and are showed in tables 7,6 and 8. As expected, foggy

Table 8: YOLOV8 results on RTTS dataset

	map50	map50-95
noisy	0.656	0.416
AllWeather	0.644	0.409
SynthRSF	0.665	0.42
AllWeather+SynthRSF	0.658	0.417

Figure 5: Qualitative results from denoising real world images

images denoised by the model that was trained on SynthRSF performed better because of the advantage in fog training data. In rain and snow noise, the model trained on both datasets outperformed the rest.

4.3.2 Benchmarking YoloV8 on SynthRSF-MM

As a partial demonstration of SynthRSF’s utility, we repeated the object detector experiment on all three kinds of noise that are included in the SynthRSF-MM dataset. The results are summarized in the table 9. Similarly to the previous COCO/RTTS experiment, the combined AllWeather+SynthRSF dataset training produces better results in snow and rain images, while SynthRSF-only training was the most beneficial in images degraded by fog.

Table 9: YOLOV8 results on SynthRSF-MM dataset

	map50	map50-95
Rain		
noisy	0.293	0.218
AllWeather	0.319	0.239
SynthRSF	0.327	0.25
AllWeather+SynthRSF	0.336	0.256
Snow		
noisy	0.303	0.224
AllWeather	0.326	0.245
SynthRSF	0.314	0.238
AllWeather+SynthRSF	0.325	0.247
Fog		
noisy	0.296	0.22
AllWeather	0.288	0.217
SynthRSF	0.307	0.227
AllWeather+SynthRSF	0.302	0.227

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented and shared a novel synthetic dataset focused on adverse conditions and incorporating variable objects, lighting, and camera position. Through the use of the advanced game engine Unreal 5.2 and 3D elements, the SynthRSF dataset more closely resembles real-world adverse weather scenes.

The SynthRSF dataset’s utility has been validated in multiple experiments: a) by training the *Trans-Weather* image denoising deep learning model in a series of both objective and subjective experiments; and b) by benchmarking a state-of-the-art object detection algorithm in its performance in the absence or presence of adverse weather conditions.

We have also presented SynthRSF-MM, a novel multi-modal dataset, which includes Depth Maps for all images, as well as pixel-level annotations for 39 object classes. Although its potential uses are many, the experiment highlights its functionality as a test set for measuring an object detector’s performance in various inputs.

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